

Balimau Putih, cultivar tolerant of rice tungro-associated viruses

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Rice cultivar Balimau Putih (IRRI Acc. no. 17204) consistently showed tungro resistance in greenhouse mass-screening tests. Its resistance to rice tungro bacilliform (RTBV) and spherical (RTSV) viruses was further evaluated by test tube inoculation and compared with resistance of susceptible TN1.

Seven-day-old seedlings, 120 for each variety, were infested with green leafhoppers *Nephotettix virescens* (5

insects/seedling) that had 4 d access to TN1 plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV. Presence of tungro-associated viruses was detected by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) of each plant 1 mo after inoculation. The relative amount of virus was determined by ELISA (absorbance value at 405 nm) at 2, 6, and 10 wk after inoculation. Height and yield were measured.

Balimau Putih was more susceptible to infection with tungro-associated viruses than TN1 (see table) but did not show symptoms typical of RTBV and RTBV+RTSV infection. Relative amounts of RTBV and RTSV were consistently lower in Balimau (see figure). Apparently, the multiplication of tungro-associated viruses was

tolerable. Height reduction due to infection was lower in Balimau Putih than in TN1. Balimau Putih also had lower yield reductions. □

Reaction of Balimau Putih and TN1 in RTBV and RTSV by test tube inoculation of RTBV and RTSV at 5 insects^a per seedling. IRRI, 1986.

Variety	Plants (no.) infected with ^b			Healthy plants (no.)	Infection (%)	Height reduction (%)		Yield reduction (%)	
	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTSV			RTBV	RTBV+RTSV	RTBV	RTBV+RTSV
TN1	87	31	0	8	93.6	41.6	21.3	90.0	50.0
Balimau Putih	46	68	3	5	95.9	11.4	5.0	18.4	1.6

^aGreen leafhopper *Nephotettix virescens* were given 4 d access to TN1 plants infected with both RTBV and RTSV. ^bTotal of 4 trials. Detected by ELISA.

Relative amounts of RTBV and RTSV in doubly infected TN1 and Balimau Putih. IRRI, 1986.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

An approach to develop gall midge (GM)-resistant rice strains

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The GM *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason (Diptera: Cecidomyiidae) is being successfully tackled through conventional breeding using major genes from known resistant donors. Some parents, like IR20 and Pelita 1/1, although susceptible, were known to possess both duplicate and complementary genes for GM resistance. The approach exploits these duplicate and complementary genes to

develop GM-resistant, high yielding cultures.

Progeny from crosses involving IR20 and two other susceptible parents (Zenith, Malagkit Sungsong) were studied. During 1975–80, single plant

progeny from F₃ to F₆ were selected under high insect pressure artificially created in the field. From 1981, single plants selected for high resistance, with semidwarf habit and other desirable agronomic traits, were bulked in F₇ and

Performance of promising GM-resistant cultures at Cuttack, India.

Designation	Cross combination ^a	Silvershoots (%)				Yield (t/ha)			Grain type ^b
		1981	1982	1983	1984	1982	1983	1984	
CR294-28-1	IR20/Zenith//MSS	1.5	0.1	1.3	0.7	3.9	4.1	3.9	LS
CR294-548	IR20/Zenith//MSS	2.6	nil	1.1	nil	4.4	4.3	4.1	LS
CR316-639	IR20/MSS	2.3	0.1	1.6	nil	4.2	4.1	4.2	LB
CR318-548-7	IR20/MSS//Zenith	1.2	nil	1.2	nil	4.0	4.2	3.6	LB
Jaya	Susceptible standard	51.1	16.6	26.6	25.8	3.1	3.1	3.0	LB
IR36	Resistant standard	1.8	0.6	1.3	nil	3.7	4.1	4.1	LS

^aMSS = Malagkit sungsong. ^bLS = long slender, LB = long bold.